

Confirmation of the occurrence of *Aphthona nigriceps* (Redtenbacher, 1842) in Hungary with an updated checklist of the genus from Hungary (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae)

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Abstract – The first verified record of *Aphthona nigriceps* (Redtenbacher, 1842) (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Galerucinae: Alticidae) from Hungary is presented with an updated checklist of *Aphthona* Chevrolat, 1836 species known from Hungary. Additional records and information of some rarely collected *Aphthona* species, including *Aphthona flaviceps* Allard, 1859, *Aphthona pallida* (Bach, 1856), *Aphthona placida* (Kutschera, 1864), and *Aphthona rugipennis* Ogloblin, 1926, are given.

Key words – Chrysomeloidea, faunistics, distribution, identification, leaf beetle

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Aphthona* Chevrolat, 1836 (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Galerucinae: Alticidae) consists of more than 330 species in the Palaearctic, Oriental, Afrotropical, and Australian Regions (BASELGA & NOVOA 2002). Altogether 186 species have been described from the Palaearctic Region (DÖBERL 2010); among these, 21 species have been recorded from Hungary (VIG 2003). Several species of *Aphthona* introduced from Europe are found in the Nearctic Region as well (BOURCHIER *et al.* 2002) and used for biological control of *Euphorbia esula*

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L. (Euphorbiaceae); one of them is *Aphthona nigriscutis* Foudras, 1860, a species introduced from Hungary to North America in 1983 as a classical biological control agent (TANSEY *et al.* 2005).

A review of the genus *Aphthona* has become necessary in Hungary, since the last summary was published more than 20 years ago by VIG (2003). The present study is based on the examination of *Aphthona* specimens preserved in the collections of the Hungarian Natural History Museum Public Collection Centre – Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest (HNHM), the Savaria Museum, Szombathely (SM) and the private collection of Márk Lukátsi, Budapest (CLM), and on literature data. As a result, the authors established an updated checklist of 22 species known to occur in Hungary. The occurrence of *Aphthona nigriceps* (Redtenbacher, 1842) is confirmed in Hungary, and *Aphthona rugipennis* Ogloblin, 1926 replaced *Aphthona aeneomicans* Allard, 1875 in the previous checklist (VIG 2003).

Specimens of *Aphthona nigriceps* were swept or singled. The genitalia were dissected in 70% ethanol and card-mounted under the specimens. The specimens were examined with Bresser Researcher ICD LED stereomicroscope and identified by the first and last authors. Photographs were taken by a Raynox Super Macro Conversion Lens DCR–250 adapter set attached to a Nikon D7200 digital camera. Voucher specimens are deposited in the HNHM and CLM. Taxa are listed in alphabetic order.

RESULTS

Aphthona flaviceps Allard, 1859

Material examined – Hungary: Pest County, Apaj, 28.VI.2020, leg. M. Lukátsi, det. L. Farina (one female, HNHM).

Remarks – This species was first included in the Hungarian leaf beetle fauna by KASZAB (1962) based on CSIKI (1905) (from Budapest and Pápa); Csiki received the data of *Aphthona flaviceps* from Ferencz Wachsmann, and did not mention voucher specimens. Wachsmann's collection ended up in the HNHM after his death; however, no specimens of this species were found in the material. Subsequently, two specimens were collected in the Fertő-Hanság National Park near Osli (VIG 2002); their current depository is unknown, they could not be found in the HNHM and in the SM. The examined specimen, collected by the last author, has been deposited in the HNHM.

Aphthona nigriceps (Redtenbacher, 1842)
(Figs 1–3)

Material examined – Hungary: Baranya County, Nagyharsány, Szársomlyó Nature Conservation Area, 45°51'23.2"N, 18°25'24.9"E, 27.IX.2024, leg. G. Tamási (one male, HNHM); same label data but leg. B. P. Schlitt (two males, CLM); Somogy County, Siófok, date unknown, leg. F. Lichtneckert (four specimens, HNHM).

Remarks – KONSTANTINOV (1998) reported this species from Hungary with a reference to GRUEV (1981), but the latter article deals with a Chinese collecting trip of P. R. Hammond, without mentioning either Hungary or *Aphthona nigriceps*.

The HNHM has four specimens of *Aphthona nigriceps* collected by Ferenc Lichtneckert; however, the location of Lichtneckert's specimens – simply labelled as "Siófok" – is not undoubtedly reliable as it was discussed by many authors (e.g., VIG 2001, SZALÓKI & MERKL 2005). Ferenc Lichtneckert lived and collected mostly in Siófok, but he travelled in various parts of the Carpathian Basin and neighbouring countries and collected many insects on these expeditions. After his death, the unlabelled specimens of his collection were all labelled with the locality "Siófok" in the HNHM, evidently partly erroneously, as the material contains several species unlikely to occur in Hungary (e.g., species of Malachiidae mentioned by SZALÓKI & MERKL (2005)). Since now it is impossible to judge whether the four *Aphthona nigriceps* specimens collected by Lichtneckert were indeed collected in Siófok or were mislabelled, we consider the specimens recently collected in Baranya County as the first verified records of the species from Hungary.

Proposed Hungarian name: "feketefejú gólyaorr-földibolha", referring to its specific epithet "nigriceps" (= black-headed) and its most common host plants *Geranium* L. (Geraniaceae).

Identification – Based on external morphological characters as well as the aedeagus, the specimens were identified as *Aphthona nigriceps* (Figs 1–3) using the work of KONSTANTINOV (1998). *Aphthona nigriceps* forms a species group with *Aphthona pallida* (Bach, 1856) and *Aphthona wagneri* (Heikertinger, 1909); these species have unique genitalia characterised by an unusually wide median lobe and two or three apical denticles. Based on the presence of three denticles, the lateral ones being as well developed as the middle one, this character makes *Aphthona nigriceps* a well distinguishable species of this group (KONSTANTINOV 1998). It can be distinguished from other Hungarian species by its clearly visible black sutural band. *Aphthona lutescens* (Gyllenhal, 1813) also has this band, but *Aphthona nigriceps* is smaller (body length less than 2 mm) and its head is black, while the body size of *A. lutescens* is 2.0–2.5 mm and its head is yellowish.

Figs 1–3. *Aphthona nigriceps* (Redtenbacher, 1842) from Nagyarsány, Hungary: 1 = male habitus, 2 = aedeagus, ventral view, 3 = labels (photos by Aranka Grabant)

Aphthona pallida (Bach, 1856)

Material examined – Hungary: Budapest, date unknown, leg. E. Kaufmann, det. Z. Kaszab (one specimen, HNHM), Komárom-Esztergom County, Pilismarót, date unknown, leg. E. Csiki, det. Z. Kaszab (one specimen, HNHM).

Remarks – Based on literature data the species was also found in the Bakony Hills near Herend (TÓTH 1979), Tihany and Veszprém (ROZNER 1990). The specimen from Herend is found in the Hungarian Natural History Museum Public Collection Centre – Bakony Natural History Museum, Zirc (Csaba Kutasi, pers. comm.). The specimens from Tihany and Veszprém were part of the private collection of Attila Podlussány and István Rozner (ROZNER 1990), whose leaf beetle collections were acquired by the SM, however, no Hungarian specimen of *Aphthona pallida* was found there.

Aphthona placida (Kutschera, 1864)

Remarks – This species has been recorded from Hungary by a few authors. CSIKI (1914) mentioned it without exact location and date and without information on deposited voucher specimens. ENDRŐDI (1985) listed three locations from the Börzsöny Hills (Pest County, Verőce, 12.VII.1951; Pest County, Szokolya, 16.VIII.1951; Nógrád County, Berkenye, 16.VIII.1951); most of the collection of Sebő Endrődi from the Börzsöny Hills are now housed in the Transvaal Museum in Pretoria, South Africa and could not be examined in course of the present study. No specimens were found in either the HNHM, SM or CLM.

Aphthona rugipennis Ogloblin, 1926

Remarks – ČIŽEK & FORNŮSEK (2000) published the first record of *Aphthona aeneomicans* from Hungary, Komárom-Esztergom County (Esztergom, 27.V.1996, one male and one female). However, BERGEAL & ČIŽEK (2003) reviewed the distribution of *Aphthona aeneomicans* and *Aphthona rugipennis* and concluded that the species living in Central Europe on *Linum hirsutum* L. (Linaceae) is *Aphthona rugipennis*. The specimens collected in Esztergom were also examined by BERGEAL & ČIŽEK (2003); however, their current location is unknown (Petr Čížek, pers. comm.). Thus, the record of ČIŽEK & FORNŮSEK (2000) pertains to *Aphthona rugipennis*, not to *Aphthona aeneomicans*.

DISCUSSION

In Europe, *Aphthona nigriceps* is known from Austria, Bosnia Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Belarus, Croatia, Czech Republic, France (including Corsica, Monaco), Great Britain (including Channel Islands), Greece (including Crete), Italy (including Sardinia, Sicily, San Marino), Crimea, Montenegro, Northern Macedonia, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey, and Ukraine (GERMANN 2011, BEZDEK & SEKERKA 2024). The species is also known from Algeria, Morocco (including Western Sahara), Tunisia, Azerbaijan, Armenia, Georgia, and Iran (BEZDEK & SEKERKA 2024).

The recently collected Hungarian specimens were found in the Szársomlyó Nature Conservation Area near Nagyharsány, which is traditionally considered as a submediterranean habitat (Fig. 4). It is part of the Villány Hills and is characterised by warm and humid climate. The mean annual temperature is 10–11°C. The sunniest period is the end of summer (DÉNES *et al.* 2010).

Fig. 4. Collecting site in Hungary, Nagyharsány, Szársomlyó Nature Conservation Area (photo by Bence Péter Schlitt)

Aphthona nigriceps can be found in open and sunny areas on sandy soil. It is an oligophagous species feeding on herbaceous Geraniaceae, mainly on *Geranium rotundifolium* L., *Geranium robertianum* L., *Geranium sanguineum* L., *Geranium pratense* L., *Geranium pusillum* L., and *Erodium cicutarium* L. (RHEINHEIMER & HASSLER 2018). *Erodium malacoides* L., *Erodium moschatum* L., and *Juncus* spp. (Juncaceae) were also recognised as food plants (BIONDI 1990; DOGUET 1994). Several of these plant species can be found in the Szársomlyó Hill area (DÉNES *et al.* 2010). The species overwinters in the adult stage. It is found in April and May as well as in autumn. Adults chew holes in the leaves of host plants, larvae are presumed to live on the roots. The imago is found in both long-winged and short-winged forms (COX 2004, 2007).

Based on the above results, an updated checklist of the Hungarian species of the genus *Aphthona* is provided:

- Aphthona abdominalis* (Duftschmid, 1825)
- Aphthona atrovirens* (Förster, 1849)
- Aphthona atrocaerulea* (Stephens, 1831)
- Aphthona cyparissiae* (Koch, 1803)
- Aphthona euphorbiae* (Schrank, 1781)
- Aphthona flava* Guillebeau, 1895
- Aphthona flaviceps* Allard, 1859
- Aphthona franzi* Heikertinger, 1944
- Aphthona herbigrada* (Curtis, 1837)
- Aphthona lacertosa* (Rosenhauer, 1847)
- Aphthona lutescens* (Gyllenhal, 1808)
- Aphthona nigriceps* (Redtenbacher, 1842)
- Aphthona nigriscutis* Foudras, 1860
- Aphthona nonstriata* (Goeze, 1777)
- Aphthona ovata* Foudras, 1860
- Aphthona pallida* (Bach, 1856)
- Aphthona placida* (Kutschera, 1864)
- Aphthona pygmaea* (Kutschera, 1861)
- Aphthona rugipennis* Ogloblin, 1926
- Aphthona semicyanea* Allard, 1859
- Aphthona venustula* (Kutschera, 1861)
- Aphthona violacea* (Koch, 1803)

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